

Suite of Dissemination Materials

MATS Deliverable 6.5

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Summary

The production of dissemination materials is a part of an overall dissemination strategy. Communication and dissemination activities accompany the project throughout its duration. This deliverable D6.5 *Suite of Dissemination Materials* provides an overview of all dissemination materials produced within the first period of the project (M1-M18) and emphasizes follow-up dissemination materials for the later phases of the project. D6.5 complements these four Deliverables that were prepared at the project inception: D7.2 *Communication Plan* in M4; D7.3 *Communication Toolkit with a Suite of Templates for Project Communication* in M6; D6.1 *Information Needs of Key Actors* in M6; D6.2 *Enhanced Engagement Strategy (Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy Plan)* in M8.

During the first period of the project, the consortium has developed different dissemination materials, including project logo, project flyer, project videos, events and news blogs, deliverables on the project website and open access platform Zenodo, peer-reviewed publications, project-related presentations, news pieces or blog posts published by partner organization communication channels, and social networks of project Twitter and LinkedIn accounts.

Some follow-up dissemination materials should be prioritised for the later phases of the project, including updated sustainable trade toolbox, practice abstract, policy brief, case study report, fact sheet, along with press release, newsletter, poster, and explanatory video. In addition, we are planning to engage with 'Horizon Results Booster', a service initiative offered by European Commission. We believe that these materials and tools are relevant and highly supportive in promoting MATS and maximizing its impact.

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¹ R = Report, P = Prototype, D = Demonstrator, O = Other

² PU = Public, CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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1. Introduction

Dissemination is an important means of communicating the project and its mission, informing the results of the project to a wide range group of stakeholders in the global food system, and promoting active participation and knowledge-sharing among far-reaching audiences. Communication and dissemination activities accompany the project throughout its duration.

This deliverable D6.5 *Suite of Dissemination Materials* is meant to constitute a collection of the dissemination materials produced within the first period of the project (M1-M18). It complements these four Deliverables that were prepared at the project inception:

- » [D7.2 Communication Plan](#) in M4, which identified the communication principles and goals, the targeted stakeholders' communication activities, and channels and means for external communication.
- » [D7.3 Communication Toolkit with a Suite of Templates for Project Communication](#) in M6, which elaborated the project internal communication platform and the main tools, materials, channels for external communication, serving as the go-to-document for all project partners.
- » [D6.1 Information Needs of Key Actors](#) in M6, which provided an overview of the interest and expectations of key actors regarding the role of MATS in fostering effective communication between different actors.
- » [D6.2 Enhanced Engagement Strategy \(Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy Plan\)](#) in M8, which covered such five elements as targeting of relevant actors for engagement, structured feedback loops with civil society organizations, case study partners and policy-makers involved in project activities, targeting of project outputs to current discourses and policy developments, using the most effective dissemination activities and forms, and monitoring of the effectiveness of engagement activities.

D6.5 describes a comprehensive overview of the entire dissemination events organized and/or attended by the consortium. To disseminate and engage more with relevant stakeholders and communities both in terms of enlargement of outreach and of quality of contents and materials, a suite of dissemination materials as follows are used:

- 1) Project logo — it is used in diverse ways by all partners.
- 2) Project flyer/leaflet — the leaflet, as a project graphic profile, is used at different events and continued for the remainder of the project.
- 3) Project videos — a series of meeting video recordings have been produced and stored on the internal platform MS Teams, with some posted on easily accessible social media. In

addition, explanatory videos describing the project objectives and expectations, as a dissemination cornerstone, are planned to be produced soon to post on the project website and social media channels, as well as at conferences and exhibitions.

- 4) Events and News blogs — these are regularly updated and illustrated at project website.
- 5) Deliverables — all submitted deliverables are kept up to date at project website, and hyperlinks to the open access platform Zenodo have been added, so that deliverables in PDF version can be downloaded by anyone interested in the project outcomes. A project-dedicated ‘MATS community’ in Zenodo has been created as open access research materials archive.
- 6) Publications — they include discussion papers, peer-reviewed publications from the consortium partners and manuscripts in progress during M1-M18. In addition, the project website presents academic publications and reports related to MATS-topics from MATS consortium partners, as well as previous studies that may be of interest to anyone interested in making agricultural trade more sustainable (“Knowledge Hub”).
- 7) Project presentations — they refer to all project-related presentations made by the consortium partners at relevant conferences/workshops/seminars etc. during the period M1-M18.
- 8) Roll-up and posters — they are an effective way to display the project’s visual identity and support project communication at events. The use of this dissemination material will be enhanced in next phase of the project.
- 9) Newsletters — the purpose of the newsletter is to disseminate information on the project to subscribers interested in the subject matter of the project and to provide regular updates on project’s developments. The use of this dissemination material will be enhanced.
- 10) Press releases — consortium partners are encouraged to inform the press about project progress and outcomes and to produce press releases periodically. Information can be published via mainstream media, project website, and partner organizations. The use of this dissemination material will be enhanced in the next phase of the project.
- 11) Social Network — MATS has been keeping up to date with Twitter and LinkedIn. Updating Twitter is useful to inform and interact with our target audience groups and their respective communities through audience engagement with regular posting and real-time feeds.

In addition to the continuation of these dissemination materials mentioned above, some follow-up dissemination materials should be prioritised for the later phases of the project, including sustainable trade toolbox (frameworks, indicators, and tools), practice abstract, and policy brief, along with enhanced press release, newsletter, poster, and explanatory video. By doing so, impact can be maximised from effective engagement and collaboration between researchers, policymakers, civil society organizations and the wider stakeholder community.

2. Dissemination materials updates

2.1. Project logo

As has been described in D7.2 (*Communication Plan*) in M4 and D7.3 (*Communication toolkit with a suite of templates for project communication*) in M6, the project logo reflects the creation of new insights, connections, gateways, and impact, with colourfulness as a symbol of achieving diversified SDGs in agricultural trade (see the MATS Logo on the right).

MS Word and PowerPoint templates of the MATS project have been provided for all project partners. The templates are used for all documentation and presentations about MATS. In addition, the project logo is also set as a virtual background for Zoom meeting (see Figure 1).

FIGURE 1. MATS PROJECT LOGO SET AS A VIRTUAL BACKGROUND FOR ZOOM MEETING

To give MATS a common image towards the outside world, to convey the project's visual identity, and to communicate it in a consistent way with a clear and recognisable brand, the use of the project logo and associated fonts (Verdana & Avenir Next) is required for written deliverables, discussing paper, reports, designing the website, and all relevant presentations etc.

2.2. Project flyer/leaflet

A flyer/leaflet is compiled to present the project brief showing its goals, key operational features, ambitions, and outputs. Meanwhile, it also provides an overview of the consortium (Complete List of Consortium Partners, see Annex 1) and contacts. This information leaflet (see Figure 2) is intended to explain the MATS project to the public and potential stakeholders. It has been used at events and continued for the remainder of the project. The electronic version is available for all MATS partners to make printed version for distribution at conferences, fairs, seminars, workshops and so on. E.g., the leaflet was printed out 25 copies to distribute at a trade workshop 'How

trade can support sustainability transitions?’ organized by Just Food on 22.9.2021 in Viikki, Helsinki. Target audiences are researchers who wish to better understand the international trade policy, WTO rules and how trade can support sustainability transitions. The link can be found [https://justfood.fi/en-US/Topics/All_news/How_could_trade_support_sustainability\(61590\)](https://justfood.fi/en-US/Topics/All_news/How_could_trade_support_sustainability(61590))

Project Brief
Helsinki 2020 – draft no. 10/20/2021, 01.07.2021 – 31.12.2024

Project goals

MATS aims to identify key leverage points for changes in agricultural trade policy that foster the positive and reduce the negative impacts of trade on sustainable development and human rights. Particular attention is paid to SDG 1 No Poverty, SDG 2 Zero Hunger and SDG 3 Good Health and Well-being, as well as SDG 13 Climate Action and SDG 15 Life on Land. Focus is on improving the governance, design and implementation of trade practices, regimes and policies at national, EU, African and global levels.

In implementation, MATS develops and pilots new tools for systemic analysis, and assessment of the interactions between agricultural trade, investments, sustainability and development.

Key operational features

The implementation of MATS comprises the following components:

- MATS METHOD FRAMEWORK: a set of 15 in-depth country, regional and product case studies to provide a deeper understanding of the conditions for sustainable trade, an integrated multi-model simulation and assessment of linkages with agricultural markets, trade and investment dynamics, and an analysis of institutional, regulatory and legal frameworks.
- EXPANDING PATHWAYS TOWARDS SUSTAINABLE TRADE: a multi-stakeholder forecasting and backcasting approach related to transformative change and social innovation, which uses novel participatory methods and platforms to explore transition pathways towards sustainable trade.
- COORDINATION AND POLICY COHERENCE: a clustering with other trade-related research projects, and promoting dialogue with sector representatives, social movements and policymakers in framing analyses, co-assessing linkages, and deriving policy recommendations.

Diagram: A flowchart showing the relationship between Mapping linkages, Assessing linkages, Expanding pathways, and Coordinating and policy coherence, all leading to 15 Case studies. The 15 Case studies are supported by Institutional, regulatory and legal frameworks, and Transition pathways and policy recommendations.

Ambitions

MATS has the ambition to set a new benchmark in trade policy analysis. It not only conducts orthodox quantitative analysis to identify major trends in international trade relations and their general effects, but also identifies impacts that trade agreements have by co-creating and applying new participatory tools and methods in trade-related analyses. MATS seeks to enrich and expand previous quantitative, economic and model-based analyses. Inter-disciplinary in approach, MATS combines analyses from agricultural economics, sustainable development research, and trade and market modelling with research on institutional, regulatory and legal frameworks to broaden and deepen earlier analyses and trade policy recommendations.

The project partners aim to inform relevant debates and policy developments based on this diverse portfolio of perspectives. MATS wants to contribute to the development of a fair-trade system that supports local livelihood and promote farmer and human rights on a global level. International and national food security regulators are considered to study the relationship between possible conflicts amongst diverging policy objectives, measures and subsidies, and their respective impact on climate mitigation efforts and the economic development of poor countries.

Outputs

The main project outputs are:

- New quantitative and qualitative insights on the interactions between agricultural markets, trade, investments, policy, environmental sustainability and human well-being, undistorted, and illustrated, by 15 in-depth case studies.
- A set of Discussion Papers and Policy Briefs on the impacts of EU, Africa and WTO policies with their interplay and trade-offs, on transition pathways for desirable changes in trade relations and instruments with recommendations for enhancing the coherence of agricultural and trade policies with sustainable development goals and policy.
- An enhanced civil society-stakeholder-policy dialogue that is supported by an evidence-based communication platform – the Sustainable Trade Hub – which fosters effective collaboration between regulators, policymakers, civil society and the wider stakeholder community.
- A set of innovation research tools for the analysis of the interactions between agricultural trade, agricultural and rural investments, and key innovation, environmental sustainability and human well-being, and a suite of communication materials on agricultural markets, trade and sustainability.

Diagram: A flowchart showing the process from Ambitions to Outputs, involving a team of researchers and stakeholders, leading to various outputs like Policy Briefs, Discussion Papers, and the Sustainable Trade Hub.

The 15 case studies

Topic	Key aspects	Main focus	Lead partner
1) Effects of trade on common-collaboration and processing of food products	Improving the livelihoods of smallholder farmers in the context of trade liberalization of food systems, strengthening of food systems, strengthening of food systems	Uganda, Tanzania	University Helsinki (UHS) with Makerere University
2) Trade, resilience and social sustainability: case studies in the Nordic	Resilience of trade-dependent food value chains in the context of major EU food trade and social sustainability, sustainability and equity	Finland, Sweden, EU	University Helsinki (UHS)
3) Trade, sustainability and environmental linkages in fresh-produce production	Mapping the linkages of dairy production and dairy trade with environmental externalities and production of non-system services	Finland, EU, India	University Helsinki (UHS) with partners
4) Assessing export markets with high sustainability commercial standards	Standards for market access: challenges related to EU rules and regulations and/or EU requirements, strengthening of national markets	Sub-Saharan Africa	Economic and Social Research Foundation (ESRF)
5) Role of agricultural inputs and policy regulation in sustainable agriculture	Emerging markets, country characteristics of policy regulation regarding input and welfare, inputs and trade complex dynamics, sustainability, livelihoods	Ghana, Ethiopia	Technical University of Munich (TUM)
6) Farm gate prices and sustainable business models to work living income	Color terms, objectives, impact and lessons learned from the cocoa sector	EU, Costa Rica	Odium WoodBusiness (OWB)
7) Impacts of EU policies on local food systems in India	EU agricultural, trade, investment and development policies impact on the development of local food and food systems	EU, Africa	Odium Solidaritas - Odium Solidarity (OSD)
8) EU climate and energy policies and their influence on trade and on	EU climate policies and measures, sustainability criteria, EU climate funding, carbon markets, EU food production and land use change	EU, America, Africa, Asia	Odium Solidaritas - Odium Solidarity (OSD)
9) Human rights and animal-welfare issues in the coffee value chain	Integrating human rights and environmental due diligence coffee chains, impact on production practices and smallholder farmers	Tanzania, EU, Ethiopia	Odium WoodBusiness (OWB)
10) Beef and policy coherence for sustainable development	EU agricultural, trade, investment and development policies impact on beef, beef, sustainable beef chains, meeting consumers and retailers	Africa, Asia	Research Centre on Animal Production, CRPA, with Wageningen G.A.P.
11) Private standards and sustainable trade	Impact of 'private/public' standards on development of local, fair, sustainable food chains, ethical trade dimensions	Africa, Asia	Research Centre on Animal Production, CRPA, with Wageningen G.A.P.
12) Ethical trade initiatives in the South African wine industry	Assessment of local and global ethical trade programmes in South Africa: King Pin, Ethical Trading Initiative, ethical trade dimensions	South Africa, Asia	Radboud University (RU)
13) Dairy production, standards and competitiveness in global markets	Laborious cases: additional costs resulting from environmental regulations, total production costs, processing margin	Africa, Asia	Research Centre on Animal Production, CRPA, with Wageningen G.A.P.
14) Changing land use trajectories due to the EU-Morocco trade agreement	The case of pork exports from Brazil to the EU trade agreement, EU-Morocco pork value chains, long and short production, international	EU, Brazil	Technical University of Munich (TUM) with Institute for Agriculture and Trade Policy (IATP)
15) The implementation of EU Trade Agreements (FTA) and their impacts	Impact of EU-FTA on income and market opportunities for farmers, retailers, traders, ecological resilience, available water capacity	EU, Africa, Asia	Transnational Institute (TI)

Consortium partners

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FIGURE 2. PROJECT FLYER/LEAFLET TO DISPLAY 'MATS PROJECT GENERAL'

2.3. Project videos

A series of meeting video recordings are produced since the implementation of the project. They are stored in internal platform MS Teams, with one published in YouTube. The following screenshots display the videos of seven project meeting during the period M1-M18.

TABLE 1. LIST OF THE PROJECT MEETING VIDEOS RECORDINGS (M1-M18)

<p><i>Project video -1. The MATS kick-off meeting for admin and financial colleagues on 24 June 2021</i></p>	<p>MATS Kick off Admin 24 June 2021</p>
<p><i>Project video -2. The MATS kick-off consortium meeting on 08 July 2021</i></p>	<p>MATS Kick-off July 8 2021</p>
<p><i>Project video -3. The MATS project meeting on 16 September 2021</i></p>	<p>September 16 meeting video</p>

Project video -4. The MATS project meeting on 03 February 2022

Project video -5. The MATS project webinar on 28 March 2022

Project video -6. The MATS project meeting on 6-7 October 2022, in Maastricht, the Netherlands Location: Crowne Plaza Hotel Maastricht

In addition, the project webinar recording on 28 March 2022 is available via MATS EU YouTube channel: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCz64Tq4I7Os9MfQaTOHPARA>

FIGURE 3. MATS EU YouTube CHANNEL

Regarding the project videos, strictly speaking, they should be explanatory videos describing the project objectives and expectations. To disseminate the project effectively, a short explanatory (explainer) video introducing MATS to present the project objectives and expectations of key stakeholders, as a cornerstone of dissemination, is planned to be produced soon to post on the project website and social media channels, as well as at conferences and exhibitions, if necessary.

2.4. Events and News blogs

Dissemination events and news blogs have been regularly updated along with the dissemination and communication activities carried out within this period. The project website illustrates major activities. A website content submission form is used for all partners to add contents to project website, including such four categories as news item, MATS related events, other events, and capacity building (see Figure 4). The 'Events' section, together with home page linking back to this section, has allowed to timely showcase the project events to further promote participation (see Figure 5).

FIGURE 4. WEBSITE CONTENT SUBMISSION FORM

FIGURE 5. SCREEN SHOT OF EVENTS AND NEWS BLOG ON THE PROJECT WEBSITE

Events, news blogs, and capacity building in the website relevant sections has been enriched, listed in the table here below.

TABLE 2. LIST OF EVENTS, NEWS BLOG, AND CAPACITY BUILDING ON THE PROJECT WEBSITE (M1-M18)

Issued Time	Title
November 4, 2022	Discussion briefs 6/2022 – Synthesis of model-based Studies: a discussion on computational models applied in agricultural trade-related work
November 2, 2022	World circular economy forum 2022 with focus on Africa
October 17, 2022	Capacity development for agricultural innovation systems (AIS) mainstreaming and investments through the tropical agriculture platform – 13th of October
October 17, 2022	Food system in Tanzania – a focus on distribution
October 17, 2022	Opening of the black sea grain corridor
October 17, 2022	TRALAC annual conference 2022, 13-14 October 2022: Africa's trade and governance agenda in a changing world
September 21, 2022	Policy seminar – leveraging data to improve intra-Africa food trade, Sep 27, 2022
July 5, 2022	Oxfam publishes its global position paper on fair trade
May 4, 2022	Report: subsidies, trade, and international cooperation
May 4, 2022	Enhancing sustainability in EU free trade agreements: the case for a holistic approach
April 26, 2022	Food and energy shortages: are trade and investment deal the solution?
March 30, 2022	Seminar: Mexico's transition from ag biotech to agroecology and challenges from U.S. Trade policy
March 30, 2022	Geopolitics of food EU response post 23/3 communication
March 29, 2022	Webinar: unpacking south Africa's Road to building back better, fairer, and greener the EU's green new deal and its implications for south Africa
March 30, 2022	MATS interactive online workshop on the 28th of March 2022
March 29, 2022	Trade and poverty: what do we know?
January 5, 2022	How can voluntary sustainability standards (VSS) contribute to poverty reduction for smallholder farmers?
December 20, 2021	EU promotes world trade organization initiatives on trade and environment
October 20, 2021	European economic and social committee (EESC) reviews the EC's 15-point action plan on trade and sustainable development (TSD) chapters – 20th of October 2021
July 8, 2021	MATS kick-off meeting – 8th of July 2021

As D7.2 and D7.3 stated that regular blog posts are to provide interested actors with the latest news and results of MATS, hence we will be benchmarked in the forthcoming mid-term review exercise in March 2023 correspondingly. Blog posts will be published on top of posting news items only, i.e., they are meant to be explanatory briefs (and/or opinion pieces of individual partners) related to the ongoing research or timely initiatives or events on sustainable agricultural trade and trade policy.

In addition, 'Overview of Case Studies and Browse by SDG's', and 'Databases, Analyses & Tools' are updated, as shown in Figure 6.

2.5. Deliverables (project website and Zenodo)

The project website has been updated with all submitted deliverables, and hyperlinks to open access platform Zenodo have been added, so that deliverables in PDF version can be downloaded by anyone interested in the project outcomes, as shown in Figure 8 and Figure 9 below.

MATS ABOUT CASE STUDIES OUTPUTS COMMUNITY EVENTS KNOWLEDGE HUB

Deliverables

- ✓ WP1 - Mapping linkages**

 - D1.1 Discussion paper and infographic(s) on the links between agricultural trade, investments, environmental sustainability and human well-being
 - D1.2 Discussion paper and infographic(s) on trends in agri-food trade
 - D1.3 Discussion paper and infographic(s) on the role of sustainability goals in trade rules
 - D1.4 Webinar to discuss the results of WP1
- ✓ WP2 - Frameworks, indicators and tools**

 - D2.1 Set of indicators for assessing the sustainability impacts of agricultural trade
 - D2.2 Synthesis of model-based studies
 - D2.3 Sustainable Trade Toolbox (update M36)
 - D2.4 Analytical framework
- ✓ WP3 - Assessing linkages**

 - D3.1 Methodological guidelines and reporting template
 - D4.5 Summary paper on the role of institutional, regulatory and legal frameworks
- ✓ WP5 - Transition pathways and policy recommendations**

 - D5.1 Vision of sustainable trade regimes (Webinar and Policy Brief)
 - D5.2 Discussion paper and set of infographics on transition pathways
 - D5.3 Discussion paper on the feasibility of changes in trade relations and instruments
 - D5.4 Set of Policy Briefs with recommendations for improving the sustainability impacts of trade regimes
- ✓ WP6 - Dialogue, dissemination and exploitation**

 - D6.1 Information needs of key actors
 - D6.2 Enhanced engagement strategy and civil society–stakeholder–policy dialogue
 - D6.3 Evidence-based communication platform: Sustainable Trade Hub
 - D6.4 Civil society–stakeholder–policy dialogue, incl. two high-level policy workshops (EU, Africa)
 - D6.5 Suite of dissemination materials
- ✓ WP7 - Project management and communication**

 - D7.1 Minutes of General Assembly
 - D7.2 Communication plan
 - D7.3 Communication toolkit with a suite of templates for all project communication
 - D7.4 Data management plan
- ✓ WP8 - Ethics and Security**

 - D8.1 Human-Requirement No.1
 - D8.2 POPD- Requirement No.2
 - D8.3 MFD- Requirement No.3

FIGURE 8. DELIVERABLES UPDATED ON THE PROJECT WEBSITE

FIGURE 9. DELIVERABLE IN PDF FORM TO BE DOWNLOADED FROM OPEN ACCESS PLATFORM ZENODO

A project-dedicated ‘MATS community’ in Zenodo has been created as open access research materials archive (see Figure 10). Besides showcasing some of the project materials (publications, public deliverables, etc.) on the project website, Zenodo, an Open Access research archive funded by CERN, the OpenAire project and the EC, is an important platform for depositing deliverables, publications and reports to increase the visibility and accessibility of materials beyond the end of the project. All peer-reviewed project publications and public deliverables are in “Open Access” mode, while the confidential deliverables involving data protection are archived in “Closed Access” or ‘Restricted Access’ mode and accessed by the Consortium only.

FIGURE 10. PREVIEW OF THE MATS COMMUNITY IN ZENODO

2.6. Publications

The project has/will continue to produce peer-reviewed publications, including journal articles and conference proceedings in the areas of agricultural trade, investment, sustainability, and corresponding institutional, regulatory and legal frameworks, transition pathways and policy recommendations. The peer-reviewed academic articles are deposited on Zenodo's MATS community and the project website and are available on an open access basis. Table 3 shows the peer-reviewed publications from the consortium partners within M18. In addition, scientific manuscripts submitted/under review/in press and discussing papers from the consortium partners are also listed (see Table 4). In contrast to these, non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publications relating to MATS are valued, including policy briefs or articles in specialist policy media, case study briefs or case study reports and fact sheets showcasing output from empirical analyses and related discussions, and essays or posts in stakeholder journals. These popularised publications are a very important part of the publications of the project results.

TABLE 3. LIST OF PEER-REVIEWED PUBLICATIONS FROM THE CONSORTIUM PARTNERS (M1-M18)

Partner name	Peer-reviewed publication title	Journal	Published time
UM Sanders, A. K.	Intellectual property in digital agriculture.	Law, Innovation and Technology. DOI: 10.1080/17579961.2022.2047522	Mar. 2022
UM Tyagi, K.	Mega Mergers in the Seeds & Agrochem Industry: Nipping the Seeds of Innovation (& Sustainability) in the Bud?	Nordic Journal of European Law, 5(1), 181-189. doi.org/10.36969/njel.v5i1.24507	Aug. 2022

TABLE 4. LIST OF MANUSCRIPTS SUBMITTED/UNDER REVIEW/IN PRESS OR OTHERS FROM THE CONSORTIUM PARTNERS (M1-M18)

Partner name	Manuscript title	Manuscript status	Submitted time
AUA: A. REZITIS, S. KARYTSAS, A.S. SIETTOU, E. XYLANGOURAS	Examining international dairy trade using the gravity framework	Under review.	Sept. 2022
AUA: A. REZITIS, S. KARYTSAS, E. XYLANGOURAS, L. ZANGELIDIS	Examining international beef trade using the gravity framework	Under review	Dec. 2022
AUA: A. REZITIS, S. KARYTSAS, E. XYLANGOURAS, L. ZANGELIDIS	Discussion briefs 6/2022 – synthesis of model-based studies: a discussion on computational models applied in agricultural trade-related work	Discussion paper: https://sustainable-agri-trade.eu/discussion-briefs-6-2022-synthesis-of-model-based-studies-a-discussion-on-computational-models-applied-in-agricultural-trade-related-work/	Jul. 2022
UH: M. CARLSON, UBERN: C. HÄBERLI UH: B. STEINER	The EU's climate package, Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) and other climate policy measures: relevance for MATS	Discussion paper	Oct. 2022
UBERN: C. HÄBERLI	Opening of the Black Sea Grain Corridor	Report: https://sustainable-agri-trade.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/10/Report.pdf	Aug. 2022
UBERN: C. HÄBERLI	Barva invest 2022 SUM UP. In Partnership with World Trade Institute under MATS Project	Report	Dec. 2022

The project website also presents academic publications and reports related to MATS-topics from MATS consortium partners, as well as previous studies that may be of interest to anyone interested in making agricultural trade more sustainable (see Figure 11).

MATS ABOUT CASE STUDIES OUTPUTS COMMUNITY EVENTS KNOWLEDGE HUB

- Databases, Analyses & Tools
- Capacity Building
- Related Publications and Reports

Related Publications and Reports

Below you will find MATS-topics related academic publications and reports, both from MATS consortium partners as well as previous studies potentially of interest to anyone interested in making agricultural trade more sustainable.

1. OECD-FAO Guidance for responsible agricultural supply chains. Dedicated website related to responsible investments with cross-references to living wages, sustainable supply chains, deforestation, etc. (OECD/FAO)
2. The global food system and nodes of power. Assessing power concentration in value chains (Hendrickson, M. et al.)

Publications on gender in value chains

1. Koerppen, D., Wakefield, S. (2017) Applying feminist principles to program monitoring, evaluation, accountability and learning. Oxfam
2. Jayasinghe, N., Parvez B., Anam Zaaroura, M. (2019) Integrating gender in research planning. Oxfam
3. Oxfam (2014a) Quick guide to gender analysis
4. Oxfam (2014b) Quick guide to gender-sensitive indicators
5. Harvey, R., Rewald, R., Safier, C., Wakefield, S. (2019) Oxfam's guide to feminist influencing. Oxfam
6. Pyburn, R. et al. (2021) Gender dynamics in value chains. Washington, DC: International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI)
7. Quisumbing, A., et al. (2021) Women's empowerment and gender equality in agricultural value chains: evidence from four countries in Asia and Africa. Food Security 13 (5): 1101-24
8. Rubin, D. et al. (2009) Promoting gender equitable opportunities in agricultural value chains: a handbook. Washington, DC: USAID

Governmental analyses, assessments and research activities

1. Harnessing Knowledge, Finnish Government
2. Sustainable Trade Unit, Ministry for Foreign Affairs of Finland
3. Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanisms and Their Economic Impact on Finland and the EU

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 101000751

FIGURE 11. SCREEN SHOT OF 'RELATED PUBLICATIONS AND REPORTS IN KNOWLEDGE HUB' AT THE PROJECT WEBSITE

2.7. Project presentations

All project-related presentations made by the consortium partners at relevant conferences/workshops/seminars etc. during the period M1-M18 are listed in Table 5.

TABLE 5. LIST OF PROJECT PRESENTATIONS BY CONSORTIUM PARTNERS (M1-M18)

Partner name	Presentation title	Conferences/workshop/seminar and links	Time
1-UH (B. Steiner)	From Sustainability at the farm gate to making agricultural trade more sustainable	Finnish Organic Research Institute (FORI) webinar series. https://luomuinstituutti.fi/luomututkimuksen-webinaarisarjasyksy-2022/?lang=fi	Nov. 2022
	MATS-related presentation, to seek knowledge exchange between projects	CIRAD at Montpellier https://www.cirad.fr/ https://europa.eu/capacity4dev/value-chain-analysis-for-development-vca4d-	Dec 2022
5-SCiO	Attending	'AI for Industry and Business' online event organized by the Hellenic Federation of Enterprises https://tinyurl.com/mrmy5s3	Mar.2022
		CivTech Alliance Global Scale-up Programme 2, Challenge 2: Green Public Procurement, Tech Online Day	Oct. 2022
9-OXFAM	Case study for milk with local partner	Setting up the case study for milk with local partner (Association pour la promotion de l'élevage au sahel et en savane) https://www.apess.org/presentation/	Nov.2022

2.8. Roll-up and Posters

The partners are encouraged to develop and share a set of roll-up stands and posters for the future conferences and workshops. The announcements poster is planned to be available in the section 'News Blogs' of the project website. In addition, a special poster will be designed towards the end of the project in occasion of the participation to EU level conferences. The Roll-up stands and posters are an effective way to display the project's visual identity and support project communication at events. The use of this dissemination material will be enhanced in the coming stages of the project.

2.9. Newsletters

The purpose of the newsletter is to disseminate information on the project to subscribers interested in the subject matter of the project and to provide regular updates on project's developments. The newsletter is available via email delivery after [subscription](#). The subscription ensures that each new issue of the newsletter is delivered directly to the subscriber's inbox. A section of the project website is dedicated to subscribing to the MATS newsletter and downloading the latest issue from the home page of the website. The newsletter has not been produced in the first phase of the MATS (M1-M18), but this dissemination tool will be utilised in the later phase and more subscribers will be attracted via stakeholder consultation and improved social media (Twitter, LinkedIn) activities. In addition, target groups will be segmented, and the results of the

newsletter will be analysed regularly to optimise impact. During the MATS project lifetime, 6 newsletters are expected to be produced and distributed among the partners and subscribers.

The newsletter will be coordinated and published by the UH with technical help from the partner SCiO. All partners are expected to contribute to the contents of the newsletter when requested. Each partner can propose content to the newsletter. The objective of the MATS newsletter is to inform stakeholders about the upcoming events, the progress of MATS, links to relevant research activities by partners and/or other relevant material (e.g., data, tools) that is of potential interest to MATS partners and stakeholders.

2.10. Press releases

Consortium partners receive basic press kit material from UH and are encouraged to inform the press about project progress and outcomes and to produce press releases periodically. Information can be published via mainstream media, project website, and partner organizations, and all relevant press releases are featured and stored in the Sustainable Agricultural Trade Hub of the MATS project. As described in D7.3 (*Communication toolkit with a suite of templates for project communication*) in M6, the template for press releases is provided to consortium partners, and it can be modified for use in the partner's own channels. A press release is normally produced when an important milestone or event is performed. The use of this dissemination material will be enhanced in the next phase of the project.

Press releases as a news piece or blog post by partner organization communication channels have been published, and a brief overview is shown in Table 6.

TABLE 6. LIST OF PRESS RELEASES BY CONSORTIUM PARTNERS (M1-M18)

Partner name	News piece title	Links	Time
1-UH	EU H2020 Making Agricultural Trade Sustainable	https://researchportal.helsinki.fi/en/projects/eu-h2020-making-agricultural-trade-sustainable	Jul 2021
	New H2020 project MATS led by Professor Bodo Steiner has kicked off in July	https://flamma.helsinki.fi/en/group/ajankohtaista/news/-/uutinen/new-h2020-project-mats-led-by-professor-bodo-steiner-has-kicked-off-in-july/21498552?	Sep 2021
2-KE	MATS-related news	https://sustainable-agri-trade.eu/food-system-in-tanzania-a-focus-on-distribution/	March 2022
3-SEATINI	Making Agricultural Trade Sustainable – Interactive Online Workshop	https://seatiniuganda.org/making-agricultural-trade-sustainable-interactive-online-workshop/	March 2022
8-ESRF	ESRF newsletter January-June 2022. Page 7	https://esrf.or.tz/index.php/newsletters/	June 2022
10-FRAUNHOFER	What are the key leverage points to make agricultural trade more sustainable? Making agricultural trade sustainable (MATS)	LinkedIn Post https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6993982059857731584/ https://www.isi.fraunhofer.de/en/competence-center/foresight/projekte/mats.html	Nov 2022

12-NWU	Special project	https://commerce.nwu.ac.za/TRADE/research	Nov 2022
13-UBERN	Repairing Broken Food Trade Routes Ukraine – Africa: CONSULTANCY	https://www.wti.org/institute/news/902/repairing-broken-food-trade-routes-ukraine-africa-consultancy/	Apr 2022
	Agri-food Trade Promotion between Ukraine and Africa	https://www.wti.org/institute/news/908/agrifood-trade-promotion-between-ukraine-and-africa/	Jun 2022
	Ukraine - Initial Market Survey: Main Agri-food Exports from Ukraine to Africa	https://www.wti.org/research/publications/1367/ukraine-initial-market-survey-main-agrifood-exports-from-ukraine-to-africa/	Jul 2022
	Wheat shipments to Egypt: deeper look	https://www.wti.org/institute/news/916/wheat-shipments-to-egypt-deeper-look/	Aug 2022
	The dangerous grain delivery from Ukraine to Turkey	https://www.wti.org/institute/news/917/dr-christian-haberli-on-the-dangerous-grain-delivery-from-ukraine-to-turkey/	Aug 2022
	Could a WTO Accession "lock in" Uzbekistan's still rather timid Agricultural Reform for 2030?	https://www.wti.org/institute/news/924/could-a-wto-accession-lock-in-uzbekistans-still-rather-timid-agricultural-reform-for-2030/	Sep 2022
	Opening of the Black Sea Grain Corridor	https://www.wti.org/institute/news/925/opening-of-the-black-sea-grain-corridor-august-2022/	Sep 2022
	Repairing Broken Food Trade Routes Ukraine – Africa: new report now published!	https://www.wti.org/institute/news/956/repairing-broken-food-trade-routes-ukraine-africa-new-report-now-published/	Nov 2022
	Report: Grain Initiative continuation to sustain exports to Africa	https://www.wti.org/institute/news/972/report-grain-initiative-continuation-to-sustain-exports-to-africa/	Dec 2022
14-UM	Making Agricultural Trade Sustainable (MATS) Project Meeting	https://www.maastrichtuniversity.nl/events/making-agricultural-trade-sustainable-mats-project-meeting	Oct 2022

2.11. Social Network (Twitter and LinkedIn updates)

Project social networks accounts have been regularly updated to share and promote the relevant dissemination activities. The project website home page is added social media bar, directly linking to social media project accounts and content archives. Building a community/being part of an already existing community is crucial for dissemination via Social Media platforms. Information about the latest updates on the website, new events, discussions and news were provided via Twitter.

Updating social networks is very useful to inform and interact with our target audience groups and their respective communities through audience engagement with regular posting and real-time feeds. Social networks have been exploited to spread around the project events and media to engage further attention and maintain interest and expectation about the project outcomes.

Our Twitter channel @MATS_H2020 is primarily for external communication and raising awareness about the project work. It provides succinct information on project work, conferences, work-

shops and discussions, and the work of others. Of particular importance in this regard are connections with others engaged in research and advocacy around agri-food markets, trade, investments, sustainable development, trade regimes, governance, and policy. Tweets are also used for event announcements and invitations. The MATS Twitter channel is planned to be a lively forum for discussion, and it has already reached more than 180 followers (see Figure 12).

FIGURE 12. MATS PROJECT TWITTER ACCOUNT

The [MATS LinkedIn channel](#) is planned for deeper discussions on agri-food trade, investment and sustainability issues with professionals interested and working in these areas (see Figure 13).

FIGURE 13. MATS PROJECT LINKEDIN ACCOUNT

All communication and dissemination activities are carried out through different types of dissemination materials described above. These are collected from all partners by using a joint Excel file

and shared with them in our internal platform MS Teams. Also, the number of target group participants involved per dissemination material is estimated. In addition to focusing on the number, reach, and other metrics of publications, workshops, seminars, etc, data from MATS' social media accounts and analytics from the MATS website are used to analyse the effectiveness and reach of information posted on these channels.

Table 7 shows quantitative metrics on number of users' engagement per dissemination material, specifically numbers of project flyer distribution, views in project YouTube video, website page views for events and news blogs, downloads of deliverables from Zenodo, persons reached in project-related presentations, subscribers to the project newsletter, press release, and followers or impressions in social media.

TABLE 7. QUANTITATIVE METRICS ON NUMBER AND REACH OF USERS ENGAGEMENT PER DISSEMINATION MATERIAL (M1-M18)

Dissemination material	Quantitative metrics on number and reach of stakeholder engagement
Project flyer/leaflet	25 copies printed out to distribute at a trade workshop within M18
Project videos	40 views in one YouTube video of the project within M18 and other project 7 videos are stored in the MS Teams internal platform, not publicly posted
Events and News blogs	13 News and Events published in the project website with 2,236 page views in total within M18
Deliverables via Zenodo	915 deliverable-downloads from Zenodo within M18
Publications	2 peer-reviewed publications, 2 manuscripts submitted, 2 discussing papers and 1 report, within M18
Project presentations	5 presentations relating to MATS in events other than project meetings within M18
Newsletters	37 subscribers to the project newsletter via project website within M18
Press releases	16 news pieces published at partner organization communication platforms within M18
Social Network (Twitter and LinkedIn)	192 followers (Twitter), and 40 Followers (LinkedIn) within M18

3. Dissemination materials follow-ups and Horizon Results Booster (HRB) channel

In addition to the continuation of these dissemination materials mentioned in Section 2 above, some follow-up dissemination materials should be prioritised for the later phases of the project. These include sustainable trade toolbox (frameworks, indicators, tools, and applications), practice abstract, and policy brief, along with enhanced press release, newsletter, poster, and explanatory video. In addition, we have discussed and are to apply to the "Horizon Results Booster" with thematically related project partners (incl. Trade4SDG, [VCA4D](#)), which is a service offered by the EU Commission to boost the exploitation potential and dissemination of the project's research results together with other EU projects of similar thematic focus. These would be profoundly instrumental in disseminating information about MATS and engaging with various stakeholders. By doing so, impact can be maximised from effective engagement and collaboration between researchers, policymakers, civil society organizations and the wider stakeholder community. Table 8 shows the list of dissemination materials follow-ups (M18-M42), and below summary information provides a brief overview.

TABLE 8. LIST OF DISSEMINATION MATERIALS FOLLOW-UPS (M18-M42)

Name of materials	Description
Tools	Sustainable Trade Toolbox for an analysis of relevant frameworks, approaches, methods, and tools to assess agri-food trade from a sustainability perspective and with a systemic view. It ranges from guiding principles and approaches to specific methods, tools, and sets indicators. The toolbox will be updated after the completion of all data-based analyses in MATS.
Practice abstracts	A short summary in a direct and easy understandable way for practitioners on the final or expected outcomes, including information about main results/outcomes of the activities (expected or final), and main practical recommendations on added value/benefit/opportunities to end-users.
Case study reports/fact sheets	Showcasing output from empirical analyses and related discussions on case studies
Policy briefs	Co-creating them with public and private sectors decision makers and civil society dialogue at high-level policy workshops in WP6, and at webinar 'Policy Coherence for Sustainable Development' in WP4.
Press releases	Produce press releases periodically about the project progress and outcomes by all consortium partners.
Newsletters	During the MATS project lifetime, at least 6 newsletters will be produced and distributed among the partners and subscribers.
Roll-ups and posters	A set of roll-up stands and posters for the future conferences and workshops.

Explanatory videos	Explanatory videos describing the project objectives and expectations, as a dissemination cornerstone, are planned to be produced to post on the project website and social media channels, as well as at conferences and exhibitions.
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4. Conclusion

Within the first period of the project (M1-M18), the consortium has implemented outreach materials targeting at various audiences to spread the MATS project results by project partners in occasion of website, webinars, conferences, social networks, and other events. These include project logo, project flyer/leaflet, project videos, events and news blogs, deliverables on the project website and open access platform Zenodo, peer-reviewed publications as well as manuscripts submitted/under review, discussing papers, and other reports related to MATS-topics, project-related presentations, press releases as news pieces or blog posts published by partner organization communication channels, social networks of Twitter and LinkedIn for informing and interacting with our target audience groups and communities.

The materials outlined in this document constitute an essential part of delivering a professional and credible project by the branding of the project and increasing the visibility of the MATS projects. All these communication and dissemination materials form the basis of a series of dissemination activities that cover key areas in the project such as research, policy, and governance, to address the audience in the most effective way and engage with all relevant stakeholders and their respective communities.

Further dissemination materials will be developed as needed throughout the lifetime of the project, tailored for specific groups to disseminate project results, inform policy and engage with end-users. The foreseen dissemination materials include an updated sustainable trade toolbox (frameworks, indicators, tools, and applications), popularised publication such as practice abstract, policy brief, case study reports, fact sheets, along with press releases, newsletters, posters, and explanatory videos.

The production of dissemination materials is a part of an overall dissemination strategy. To attract targeted stakeholders, multiple dissemination actions are required. We believe that these tools are relevant and highly supportive in promoting MATS and maximizing its impact.

Annex 1. Complete List of Consortium Partners

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 University of Helsinki (UH), Department of Economics and Management, Finland (project coordinator).
-
 KnowlEdge Srl (KE), Italy.
-
 Southern and Eastern Africa Trade Information and Negotiations Institute (SEATINI), Uganda.
-
 Research Centre on Animal Production, C.R.P.A. SPA, Department of Economics and Engineering (CRPA), Italy.
-
 SCiO – Big Data Analytics in Food Systems (SCiO), Greece.
-
 Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Spain.
-
 Transnational Institute (TNI), The Netherlands.
-
 The Economic and Social Research Foundation (ESRF), Tanzania.
-
 Oxfam Solidarité - Oxfam Solidariteit (OSOL), Belgium.
-
 Fraunhofer Institute for Systems and Innovation Research ISI (FRAUNHOFER), Germany.
-
 Geoponiko Panepistimion Athinon (AUA), Department of Agricultural Economics and Rural Development, Greece.
-
 North-West University (NWU), TRADE Research Focus Area, South Africa.
-
 Universität Bern (UBERN), World Trade Institute, Switzerland.
-
 Maastricht University (UM), Faculty of Law, The Netherlands.